

THEORETICAL APPROACHES TO THE PREPARATION OF THE FUTURE TECHNOLOGY TEACHER FOR PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITIES AIMED AT SOCIALIZING STUDENTS BASED ON THE GENDER APPROACH

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Abstract: In this article discusses the theoretical approaches and mechanisms of preparing students for pedagogical activities aimed at socialization based on the gender approach.

Key words: Educational system, Technological education, gender approach, pedagogical activity, mechanism, concept.

Introduction:

Pedagogical activity is becoming one of the leading directions in the formation of a person of the new millennium, a person with high spirituality, ethnic culture, and the ability to think unconventionally. A person who strives for self-development, self-determination, self-education, self-organization. Interest in the problem of professional training of teachers is very urgent. Analysis of database sources shows that many scientists are working on this problem: teachers, philosophers, psychologists and practicing teachers. Candidate and doctoral theses are devoted to this topic. "What should a teacher of the 21st century be like?", "What training is needed?", "What professional and personal qualities should a teacher have in modern society?" These questions go beyond the scope of the traditional highly specialized system. Philosophers, sociologists, practice-oriented teachers, research scientists, as well as the psychology and medical community, are increasingly interested in the concept of "teacher development". Sustained interest is explained by the importance of the teacher in the life of society. Not only the social education of a person, but also the future of the country depends on his professional skills, moral qualities, civic consciousness. The existing liberal market policy in society affirms values that are incompatible with the true role of man and his historical culture. In our opinion, B.P. Bederkhanova expresses herself very clearly in this matter and emphasizes that there is a difference between universal human values and values of socio-cultural reality. Therefore, the future of our country and its main social institution - the family - depends strongly on what worldview, moral values and positions the young generation accepts and rethinks.

Note that pedagogic education always corresponds to the social policy of the state, is inextricably linked with it, and at the same time fulfills its command to form a certain type of personality, and is related to the role of the family, the person in the family. continued to confirm historical traditions. Therefore, considering the problem of training teachers of the 21st century, we proceed from the meanings and values developed by the previous generation, which the teacher of this century should carry. Thinking about this, L. N. Tolstoy wrote that if a teacher only has love for his profession, then it is not enough. "If a teacher has

the love of a father or mother for a student, he will be better than a teacher who has read all the books but has no love for the business or the students. If a teacher combines both love for business and love for students, he is the perfect teacher."¹. These ideas have not lost their relevance today.

Thus, the "perfect teacher" is a manifestation of the newly emerging best things accumulated in the historical experience of a particular people and corresponding to the logic of the development of human culture. The teacher's professional training starts from the university wall. A student's attitude to pedagogical activity and the ability to form his personal and professional qualities depend on the professional relations (values) created by the higher professional education system, which create conditions for the search for the personal meaning of the profession. For the sake of fairness, we note that the provisions of the "Concept of Teacher Education Development", developed in the Soviet era, prepared by leading local pedagogic scientists, focusing on the importance of the teaching profession, remain relevant. The presented document testifies to the high goal of the teacher who penetrated into the complex spiritual world of man and his boundless faith in man. In it, the teacher emphasizes that it is not just a profession, it is a state of mind, its purpose is to create a person, to confirm a person in a person.

The acquired values of graduate students serve as a vector for his social activity and allow him to meet social, material and spiritual needs. According to O. M. Krasnoryadtseva, values determine the professional direction, the active nature of behavior.

Meanings and values were formed throughout the historical development of society, carefully preserved and passed from generation to generation. The meaning and values of any people are its archetypal core, which does not allow to disappear in the evolutionary development of humanity. Let's look at the origins of teacher training, the meanings and values included in the historical and pedagogical retrospective of the society and state. The purpose of the teacher, the essence of the teaching profession, the emergence and development of ideas about the professional development of the teacher refer to the monuments of ancient culture, folklore and works of Russian folklore.

According to our research, the educational system is considered through the category of national (state) and ethnic (people) meanings and values. By the national education system, we understand the development of cultural experience, relations with the world and methods of interaction that contribute to the development of humanity, help to form a holistic system of the individual and society. The national state of a person is expressed in the national soul, as the meaning-forming beginning of the vital forces of the national culture, as a unique expression of ethnic identity. It was an ethnic principle that manifested the vital forces of the individual. Thinking about the judgments of Russian scientists about the teacher, we can talk about the predominance of the male direction of this profession. Here, the influence of the state on the topic of male education due to the historical traditional consolidation of gender roles in culture, gender stereotypes is observed.²

Emphasis is placed on the formation of behavioral norms and practical skills necessary for future defenders of the family hearth. Nevertheless, in Smolny, attention and knowledge

¹ Толстой, Л. Н. Воспитание и образование. Педагогическая хрестоматия / под ред. Н. Н. Завьялова. — М., 1908. — С. 481^497.

² Исторический альманах / авторы проекта: А. Кушнер, В. Чумаков. — М.: Народное образование, 2000. — 00 с.

are given to the French language, dancing, playing instruments, singing, and secular behavior. The elite's perfect command of the French language surprised foreigners, but as many famous intellectuals of the time noted, the replacement of the mother tongue with a foreign language was a threat to the preservation and development of the unique Russian national culture.

As we continue to analyze the content of education in women's educational institutions, we note that it was somewhat superficial in the context of learning basic sciences. For example, the study of physics lacked a scientific context because it was reduced to comic experiments, and we see the same situation in the study of history and mathematics. Official pedagogy explained the convenience of learning programs with the need to take into account "specific features of female nature." To some extent, this can be explained by the specific characteristics of the era.

When thinking about the first state women's educational institution, it is necessary to talk about the activities of Russian teachers and scientists, such as K.D. Ushinsky, N.A. Vishnegradsky, who gave more importance to the development of women's education. The fact is that great teachers focused on the humanitarian paradigm of education, including the problem of women's education. Building the educational process based on the psyche of the child, individual approach to teaching, spiritual development of students based on national cultural traditions - these and other questions worried teachers of the 19th century. Analyzing the educational process in A.K. Ushinsky thinks about instilling love for teaching by introducing the teaching of pedagogy in the secondary school. This position of the great teacher can be explained by his desire to observe socio-cultural traditions in the development of Russian society and the role of women in it. According to him, a woman is a natural nurturer.

Based on the spiritual identity of the students, At the K.D. Ushinsky Noble Institute for Girls, he implements didactic principles, focusing on the personality of the child, his needs, interests, and the moral aspects of the feminine essence of "Smolyankas".

The Russian society of the 18th and 19th centuries severely ridiculed girls who were inclined to study seriously, and imposed more moral and aesthetic requirements. The manifestation of female independence was considered inappropriate for pre-revolutionary society. In this regard, the well-known noble publicist and historian M. M. Shcherbatov notes that neither scientists nor noble girls came out of the walls of the Smolny Institute.³

This attitude towards the women's educational institution is explained by the fact that the state policy of that time had a character that corresponded to the socio-historical life of the Russian people, combined class differences, gave a different meaning to female education, to the family hearth, to the family hearth. can be explained by the fact that he paid attention to values and raising children. At the same time, we must not forget that the creation of Smolny was a breakthrough in the field of women's enlightenment. The first female translators, writers, playwrights, teachers, scientists, actresses - this is an incomplete list of professions that graduated from the institute of noble girls. This shows the positive value of the first closed women's educational institution, which included a certain element of the intellectual and moral development of Russian society, and showed the high role of women in its life.

³ Щербатов, М. М. О повреждении нравов в России. —СПб., 1858. — С. 491.

Some of the graduates of Smolny founded educational institutions for their funds and became heads of women's gymnasiums.

If we talk about the training of teachers in closed male educational institutions, then the cadet corps intended for training the military soon began to train educated nobles in a broad sense. This means that the professional activities of that period already included various educational activities, from minister to artist, from military to civilian, which fully corresponded to the reality and spirit of that time. The approved system of public education, taking into account the historical traditions of the development of the Russian society and state, has its own multi-level educational institutions that contain specific features that reflect the structure and state of the state and society found expression: property, Profile orientation, gender orientation, etc.

The encyclopedic nature of education, the fundamentalism of knowledge, taking into account the psychological characteristics of the nobility - all this showed an adequate level of training in male educational institutions, corresponding to the difficulties of that time.

Further analysis of teacher training in the context of a gender approach shows the expansion of the female education system. In the middle of the 19th century (1862), the Marinsky gymnasiums began to work with a seven-year term of study, aimed at training people's teachers. In addition, students who expressed interest in the teaching process within these educational institutions could complete the additional eighth grade and receive the title of home coaches and teachers.

Of course, the breakthrough in the training of pedagogical personnel in the 19th century is the opening of Moscow Higher Women's Courses, which laid the foundation for higher women's education in Russia. Please note that in the educational process, much attention was paid to the psychological and pedagogical block, not to a special topic. Fundamental training was provided by a high level of teaching staff, which was a novelty for that time, because the quality of teaching in women's educational institutions was traditionally much lower than in men's. A special feature of the Ministry of Internal Affairs is that during the preparation period, trainees pay constant attention not only to work at school, but also to the creation of family and marital relationships. The system of education and upbringing existing in women's courses created conditions that helped its listeners to think about the rational upbringing of their children in the future. fully corresponded to the ideological direction of his teachers.

A bright trace in the development of secondary and higher pedagogical education in the pre-revolutionary period was left by the Bestuzhev higher women's courses. For more than 30 years, about 4,000 people have graduated from Bestuzhev's courses. Two thirds of them devoted themselves to pedagogical activities. Graduates are qualified to teach in all grades of female high schools and four sub-grades of male high schools.

Note that by the 19th century. two approaches were formed in the development of women's education and the training of female pedagogical personnel: progressive and traditional. Actively supporting these views of K. D. Ushinsky, the famous pedagogue V. P. Ostrogorsky women's gymnasium helped to eliminate the differences in the education of men and women, which proved the development of both. However, despite having access to education, its importance is that a woman should always remain a woman. The ideal of wife and mother cannot be harmed by raising the ideal of woman as a human being. The

rapprochement of the two sexes in general spiritual processes should raise the moral level not only of the family, but also of the society⁴.

It should be noted that the statements of the famous teacher are still relevant at the beginning of the 21st century. The fact is that, having reached the heights of career growth, a woman achieves a certain level of professionalism, she takes the vector of development on her own. builds in the direction of self-education, self-determination, self-organization. At the same time, the issues of family and marital relations will be less important for him compared to professional self-realization, which will negatively affect the demographic picture of society, the stability of its main social institution - the family institution.

At the same time, with the revolutionary change of social conditions, changes in gender education are observed in, corrections are made to gender roles, gender stereotypes, and society forces to change the entire national education system. After the revolution, some schools were closed. From this moment, joint education is introduced to boys and girls, which is aimed at educating the working masses, without taking into account the psychological characteristics of gender⁵. With the era of co-education, the paradigm of life-building was confirmed, where all citizens of both sexes are equal builders of a communist society. The labor school of the state educates a new type of the young generation, the builders of communism, on the basis of models, uniform plans and uniform programs. Accordingly, pedagogical universities do not pay attention to the formation of models of masculinity and feminism, male and female qualities, because the content of the educational process is subordinated to the formation of workers and builders of a new society.

Thus, we can conclude that the birth, formation and development of the educational system in society and the state, as well as the training of pedagogical personnel, took place within the originally defined historical path of the formation of Russian culture.

⁴ Острогорский, В. П. 25-летие женских гимназий // Вестник Европы. —1883. —№ 4. —С. 59-62.

⁵ Львов, К. И. Совместное обучение в прошлом и настоящем // Советская педагогика. —1945. —№ 7. —С. 39-45.

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